

On the value distribution properties of the Smarandache double-factorial function

Jianping Wang

College of Science, Chang'an University, Xi'an, 710064, P.R.China

Abstract For any positive integer n , the famous Smarandache double-factorial function $SDF(n)$ is defined as the smallest positive integer m , such that $m!!$ is divisible by n , where the double factorial $m!! = 1 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdots m$, if m is odd; and $m!! = 2 \cdot 4 \cdot 6 \cdots m$, if m is even. The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary and analytic methods to study the value distribution properties of $SDF(n)$, and give an interesting mean value formula for it.

Keywords The Smarandache double-factorial function, value distribution, mean value, asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction and results

For any positive integer n , the famous Smarandache double-factorial function $SDF(n)$ is defined as the smallest positive integer m , such that $m!!$ is divisible by n , where the double factorial

$$m!! = \begin{cases} 1 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdots m, & \text{if } m \text{ is odd;} \\ 2 \cdot 4 \cdot 6 \cdots m, & \text{if } m \text{ is even.} \end{cases}$$

For example, the first few values of $SDF(n)$ are:

$$\begin{aligned} SDF(1) &= 1, SDF(2) = 2, SDF(3) = 3, SDF(4) = 4, SDF(5) = 5, SDF(6) = 6, \\ SDF(7) &= 7, SDF(8) = 4, SDF(9) = 9, SDF(10) = 10, SDF(11) = 11, SDF(12) = 6, \\ SDF(13) &= 13, SDF(14) = 14, SDF(15) = 5, SDF(16) = 6 \cdots \cdots \end{aligned}$$

In reference [1] and [2], F.Smarandache asked us to study the properties of $SDF(n)$. About this problem, some authors had studied it, and obtained some interesting results, see reference [3]. In an unpublished paper, Zhu Minhui proved that for any real number $x > 1$ and fixed positive integer k , we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} SDF(n) = \frac{5\pi^2}{48} \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{a_i \cdot x^2}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where a_i are computable constants.

The other contents related to the Smarandache double-factorial function can also be found in references [4], [5], [6] and [7]. For example, Dr. Xu Zhefeng [4] studied the value distribution problem of the F.Smarandache function $S(n)$, and proved the following conclusion:

Let $P(n)$ denotes the largest prime factor of n , then for any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (S(n) - P(n))^2 = \frac{2\zeta\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{3 \ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln^2 x}\right),$$

where $\zeta(s)$ denotes the Riemann zeta-function.

The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary and analytic methods to study the value distribution problem of the double-factorial function $SDF(n)$, and give an interesting asymptotic formula it. That is, we shall prove the following conclusion:

Theorem 1. For any real number $x > 1$ and any fixed positive integer k , we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (SDF(n) - P(n))^2 = \frac{\zeta(3)}{24} \frac{x^3}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{c_i \cdot x^3}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where $P(n)$ denotes the largest prime divisor of n , and all c_i are computable constants.

Now we define another function $S(n)$ as follows: Let $S(n)$ denotes the smallest positive integer m such that $n \mid m!$. That is, $S(n) = \min\{m : n \mid m!\}$. It is called the F.Smarandache function. For this function, using the method of proving Theorem 1 we can also get the following:

Theorem 2. For any real number $x > 1$ any fixed positive integer k , we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (SDF(n) - S(n))^2 = \frac{\zeta(3)}{24} \frac{x^3}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{c_i \cdot x^3}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right).$$

§2. Proof of the theorems

In this section, we shall prove our theorems directly. First we prove Theorem 1. We separate all integers n in the interval $[1, x]$ into two subsets A and B as follows: $A = \{n : 1 \leq n \leq x, P(n) > \sqrt{n}\}$; $B = \{n : 1 \leq n \leq x, n \notin A\}$, where $P(n)$ denotes the largest prime divisor of n . If $n \in A$, then $n = m \cdot P(n)$ and $P(m) < P(n)$. So from the definition of A we have $SDF(2) = 2$. For any positive integer $n > 2$ and $n \in A$, $SDF(n) = P(n)$, if $2 \nmid n$.

$SDF(n) = 2P(n)$, if $2 \mid n$. From this properties we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in A}} (SDF(n) - P(n))^2 \\ &= \sum_{\substack{2n \leq x \\ 2n \in A}} (SDF(2n) - P(2n))^2 + \sum_{\substack{2n-1 \leq x \\ 2n-1 \in A}} (SDF(2n-1) - P(2n-1))^2 \\ &= \sum_{\substack{n \leq \frac{x}{2} \\ 2n \in A}} (SDF(2n) - P(2n))^2 = \sum_{\substack{1 < n \leq \frac{x}{2} \\ 2n \in A}} (2P(2n) - P(2n))^2 \\ &= \sum_{\substack{1 < n \leq \frac{x}{2} \\ 2n \in A}} P^2(2n) = \sum_{\substack{np \leq \frac{x}{2} \\ p > 2n}} p^2 = \sum_{n \leq \frac{\sqrt{x}}{2}} \sum_{2n < p \leq \frac{x}{2n}} p^2. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

By the Abel's summation formula (See Theorem 4.2 of [8]) and the Prime Theorem (See Theorem 3.2 of [9]):

$$\pi(x) = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{a_i \cdot x}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where a_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) are constants and $a_1 = 1$.

We have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{2n < p \leq \frac{x}{2n}} p^2 &= \frac{x^2}{(2n)^2} \cdot \pi\left(\frac{x}{2n}\right) - (2n)^2 \cdot \pi(2n) - 2 \int_{2n}^{\frac{x}{2n}} y \cdot \pi(y) dy \\ &= \frac{x^3}{24n^3 \ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{b_i \cdot x^3 \cdot \ln^i n}{n^3 \cdot \ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{n^3 \cdot \ln^{k+1} x}\right), \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where we have used the estimate $2n \leq \sqrt{x}$, and all b_i are computable constants.

Note that $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^3} = \zeta(3)$, from (1) and (2) we have

$$\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in A}} (SDF(n) - P(n))^2 = \frac{\zeta(3)}{24} \frac{x^3}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{c_i \cdot x^3}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right), \tag{3}$$

where all c_i are computable constants.

For any positive integer n with $n \in B$, it is clear that $SDF(n) \ll \sqrt{n} \cdot \ln n$ and $P(n) \ll \sqrt{n}$. So we have the estimate

$$\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in B}} (SDF(n) - P(n))^2 \ll \sum_{n \leq x} n \cdot \ln^2 n \ll x^2 \cdot \ln^2 x. \tag{4}$$

Combining (3) and (4) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} (SDF(n) - P(n))^2 &= \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in A}} (SDF(n) - P(n))^2 + \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in B}} (SDF(n) - P(n))^2 \\ &= \frac{\zeta(3)}{24} \frac{x^3}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{c_i \cdot x^3}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right), \end{aligned}$$

where all c_i are computable constants. This proves Theorem 1.

Now we prove Theorem 2. Note that $S(n) - P(n) = 0$, if $n \in A$; and $|S(n) - P(n)| \ll \sqrt{n}$, if $n \in B$. So from the result of the reference [4] and the proving method of Theorem 1 we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} (SDF(n) - S(n))^2 &= \sum_{n \leq x} (SDF(n) - P(n))^2 + \sum_{n \leq x} (S(n) - P(n))^2 \\ &\quad - 2 \sum_{n \leq x} (S(n) - P(n)) \cdot (SDF(n) - S(n)) \\ &= \frac{\zeta(3)}{24} \frac{x^3}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{c_i \cdot x^3}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 2.

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